

Investigating the Impact of Data Storage Mechanisms on Distributed Software-Defined Networking Controllers Performance

Kang Xingyuan
Information Science
Nara Institute of Science and Technology
Ikoma, Japan
kang.xingyuan.ku3@naist.ac.jp

Keichi Takahashi
D3 Center
University of Osaka
Osaka, Japan
takahashi.d3c@osaka-u.ac.jp

Chawanat Nakasan
Computer Engineering
Kasetsart University
Bangkok, Thailand
chawanat.n@ku.th

Kohei Ichikawa
Information Science
Nara Institute of Science and Technology
Ikoma, Japan
ichikawa@is.naist.jp

Hajimu Iida
Information Science
Nara Institute of Science and Technology
Ikoma, Japan
iida@itc.naist.jp

Abstract—The rapid expansion of IoT devices and the exponential growth of global data traffic necessitate advanced data storage and management solutions. Distributed Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has emerged as a promising approach, integrating distributed storage and network control mechanisms to enhance scalability and reliability. ONOS, a widely adopted SDN controller, employs the Atomix distributed datastore to maintain network state consistency using the Raft consensus algorithm. However, the complex synchronization processes in ONOS/Atomix architecture introduce latency and inefficiencies, particularly in large-scale networks. This study investigates alternative storage mechanisms within ONOS/Atomix, analyzing their impact on network performance. Leveraging the Flow Setup Time (FST) model, we evaluate different data consistency models and synchronization strategies to optimize SDN controller operations. Our findings highlight the challenges posed by Atomix’s strong consistency requirements and propose potential improvements for balancing synchronization frequency and system efficiency. By refining data storage and retrieval mechanisms, this research aims to enhance the performance of distributed SDN architectures in handling large-scale network demands.

Index Terms—Distributed Software-Defined Networking Environment, Inter-Communication Mechanism, Consistency Models, Data Storage Mechanisms, Information Synchronization

I. INTRODUCTION

In the current era of big data, the widespread use of network devices generates an enormous amount of data every moment, presenting significant challenges in data storage, efficient management, and security. According to reports, the global number of Internet of Things (IoT) devices reached 18.8 billion in 2023¹, with an annual growth rate of 13%, a trend expected to continue². Similarly, data from the Ericsson

Mobility Report highlight that global mobile data traffic is growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 19%, with projections suggesting that it will expand 2.5 to 3 times by 2030, reaching approximately 303 exabytes per month by 2024 (excluding fixed wireless access)³. These trends underscore the increasing demand for efficient data storage and management solutions.

To tackle the challenges associated with storing, retrieving, and securing the large volumes of data generated by IoT devices, a range of advanced technologies has been developed. **Distributed storage systems**, using techniques such as data sharding and replication, improve scalability and ensure data reliability by distributing data across multiple locations. **Software-Defined Networking (SDN)** and **Network Function Virtualization (NFV)** decouple network management and functionality from hardware, enabling greater flexibility, dynamic resource allocation, and scalability in handling large data flows. Meanwhile, **edge computing** brings data processing closer to the source, significantly reducing latency and alleviating bandwidth demand, which is critical for real-time applications. Together, these technologies represent a multifaceted approach to overcoming the complex challenges posed by the modern data explosion. Among these, **distributed SDN** integrates distributed systems and software-defined networking with cloud-based storage, attracting significant attention in the research community.

In distributed SDNs, ensuring the efficiency and reliability of the entire network requires multiple SDN controllers to maintain a consistent network view through consensus algorithms, leading to additional communication overhead

¹<https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/network-devices-global-market-report>

²<https://iot-analytics.com/number-connected-iot-devices/>

³<https://www.ericsson.com/en/reports-and-papers/mobility-report/dataforecasts/mobile-traffic-forecast>

and latency between controllers, particularly in large-scale networks. Additionally, as network demands increase, unpredictable workloads can result in longer message processing times, increased queuing delays, or even controller failures. To achieve efficient and stable controller operations in a distributed SDN, implementing an appropriate data storage mechanism is essential. The method of data storage in distributed SDNs can significantly influence the processing time of network information, such as the processing priority of network data. Lower-priority requests are typically processed with delays, leading to longer queuing delays and, consequently, degrading overall network performance.

Fig. 1. ONOS/Atomix Architecture

In the domain of distributed SDN, OpenDaylight (ODL) [1] and Open Network Operating System (ONOS) [2] lead the adoption and popularity, surpassing other distributed SDN controllers. Compared to ODL, ONOS offers greater scalability and robustness [3], allowing network operators and researchers to design and customize networks according to diverse requirements. This flexibility makes ONOS highly suitable for networks of various scales and use cases. In addition, ONOS benefits from a vibrant developer community and active contributor ecosystem, ensuring continuous platform improvement and innovation. A key feature that attracts researchers to ONOS is its novel distributed key/value datastore, Atomix, which streamlines controller management, ensures data consistency across controllers, and optimizes transaction processing. In the ONOS/Atomix architecture as shown in Fig. 1, a cluster of multiple Atomix nodes serves as the East-West interface, maintaining a consistent network state across controllers leveraging the Raft consensus algorithm (the details will be shown below, in Section III). This architectural division allows the ONOS to offer greater scalability and flexibility, making it a promising framework for distributed SDNs. However, the communication between ONOS and Atomix clusters is highly complex, posing significant research challenges. This research exploring alternative storage mech-

anisms within ONOS to analyze their impact on distributed SDN performance.

II. RELATED WORK

Research on the storage mechanisms in the latest version of ONOS is scarce. In research [4], Zhang et al. investigate the impact of inter-domain synchronization levels on the performance of distributed SDN architectures. They develop a generic network model incorporating link preferences for path construction and establish analytical lower bounds to quantify routing performance under varying synchronization statuses. Their analysis reveals that increased synchronization does not always lead to better performance; instead, the optimal synchronization level depends on specific network parameters and structural properties. For instance, in networks with certain topologies, excessive synchronization can lead to unnecessary overhead without significant performance gains. These findings provide fundamental guidance for SDN performance analysis and protocol design.

Moreover, Poularakis et al. [5] address the challenge of determining the optimal frequency of synchronization message dissemination between controller pairs. They formulate the SDN synchronization problem with two objectives: maximizing the number of synchronized controller pairs and enhancing the performance of applications affected by synchronization rates. Utilizing techniques from knapsack optimization and learning theory, they derive algorithms with provable performance guarantees for each objective. Evaluation results demonstrate significant benefits over baseline schemes that synchronize all controller pairs at equal rates. Specifically, their approach achieves improved application performance and resource efficiency by tailoring synchronization rates to the dynamics of individual controller pairs.

The study most closely related to this research is by A. S. Muqaddas et al. [6], which explores the inter-controller traffic required to maintain consistency in ONOS clusters using the Ibit version of ONOS. Their work focuses on the consistency challenges within distributed SDN environments and examines how the multi-controller systems utilize inter-controller communication to ensure network state consistency. The authors begin by conducting an in-depth analysis of ONOS and summarizing its primary distributed datastores, as shown in Table I, this table shows various distributed datastores used to store specific types of network information. The priority and mode of storing different types of network information are determined by the protocols and associated consistency models. Based on real traffic measurements and analysis of the adopted consistency protocols, such as the Raft and anti-entropy protocols, the authors quantify the characteristics of inter-controller traffic under different network topologies and load conditions. They also analyze the impact of factors such as controller-to-controller latency, shared data structure design, current network state (e.g., topology), and network events (e.g., flow or host additions) on traffic patterns and consistency levels. Ultimately, their findings offer a deeper understanding of inter-controller traffic behavior within ONOS

TABLE I
DATA STORAGE MECHANISMS IN ONOS (IBIS VERSION)

Distributed Datastore Name	Purpose	Protocol	Consistency Model
Mastership	Keeps the mapping between each switch to its master controller	Raft	Strong
Network Topology	Describes links and switches	Anti-entropy	Eventual
Flow	Backing flows of each switch from master to slave controller	Raft Anti-entropy	Strong Eventual
Host	Maintains list of network hosts	Raft Raft	Strong Strong
Application	Manages inventory of apps	Anti-entropy	Eventual
Component Configuration	Stores system-wide configurations	Anti-entropy	Eventual
Network Configuration	Stores network configurations	Raft	Strong

clusters, providing valuable insights for optimizing the design of distributed SDN control planes and selecting appropriate consistency protocols. However, with the introduction of the Atomix cluster in the latest version of ONOS, a re-examination of the storage mechanisms in ONOS has become necessary.

Our previous study [7] focused on optimizing controller placement in distributed SDN environments. Specifically, the previous study employed multi-objective optimization techniques to address the Controller Placement Problem (CPP), achieving efficient controller allocation and enhanced performance. The study also investigated and summarized the communication between controllers within the ONOS/Atomix architecture. Based on the observed characteristics of ONOS/Atomix, a model for measuring controller performance, Flow Setup Time (FST), was proposed. Compared to traditional methods, the key improvement of this work lies in balancing critical factors, such as network latency and controller load, through advanced multi-objective optimization. This approach resulted in more effective controller placement strategies. By analyzing and visualizing these placement strategies, this study provided valuable insights into improving the overall efficiency and performance of distributed SDN architectures. In this research, we will continue to use FST as a performance metric for controllers.

III. PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

Distributed SDN architectures, such as ONOS/Atomix, rely on consensus algorithms to synchronize network state. Our research aims to evaluate how different consistency models, synchronization level, and synchronization rate on various datastores or topologies impact network performance. To conduct this research, we have divided our work into three phases: investigation, experimentation, and large-scale simulation deployment. Currently, we are still in the first phase. Therefore, we first aim to present the challenges and issues encountered in our investigation of communication between Atomix and ONOS, as well as Atomix's synchronization process. Understanding these aspects is crucial for guiding

Fig. 2. Comparison of Consistency Models

further research. The second and third phases of the research will be discussed in Section IV.

A. Challenges in Consistency Model Selection

This study builds upon previous research [7] by utilizing the Flow Setup Time (FST) model, which has been proposed as a metric for evaluating controller performance. It continues to leverage a previously studied distributed SDN architecture, the ONOS/Atomix architecture. Within this architecture, various storage mechanisms are applied to facilitate comparisons between datastores, analyzing their advantages and disadvantages to draw meaningful conclusions. In previous research, we identified the optimal placement of controllers and datastores by considering multiple factors to enhance the efficiency of controllers in handling network events. One interesting observation from this study was that the optimal solutions consistently included a relatively small number of datastores, typically around three. This is unfavorable for large-scale networks, as rapid data growth increases the time required for controllers to process network events and for datastores to synchronize information. However, the small number of datastores in the optimal solutions was primarily due to the default settings in the ONOS/Atomix architecture, where communication between controllers and datastores is randomized.

To address this, we conducted further research into the Atomix cluster (datastore cluster) within the ONOS/Atomix architecture. We found that synchronization of network information among datastores primarily relies on the Raft consensus algorithm, which defines different consistency models for various types of network information. Specifically, the two main models are the Strong Consistency Model and the Eventual Consistency Model. As the names suggest, network information under the Strong Consistency Model has higher synchronization priority. The difference between these two models is illustrated in Fig. 2, in the diagram, D1, D2, and D3 represent datastores, where D2 is the leader and D1 and D3 are followers. When new information is updated, the leader (D2) requests the followers (D1 and D3) to update as well. Under the Strong Consistency Model, when D2 updates the value of x at time T2 and requests D1 and D3 to update, the values of x in D1 and D3 cannot be accessed until the update is

Fig. 3. Challenges in ONOS/Atomix Architecture

completed. In contrast, under the Eventual Consistency Model, the values of x in D1 and D3 can be read and written at any time. Consequently, critical network information is typically assigned to the Strong Consistency Model, while less critical information is assigned a lower priority.

B. Challenges in ONOS/Atomix Architecture

Atomix is a distributed systems framework that provides tools for building reliable and scalable ONOS applications. Despite its advantages in managing distributed state synchronization, Atomix faces several challenges that impact its performance in distributed SDN environments.

One of the major issues in Atomix is the overhead caused by data synchronization between nodes. Since Atomix enforces strong consistency, any update made on one node must be replicated across the entire cluster to ensure that all nodes have the same state. Specifically, we found that in ONOS/Atomix architecture [7], the consistency model affects the processing of network events as illustrated in Fig. 3: when request 1 is sent to the architecture, the controller immediately updates the content of request 1. However, even if request 2 occurs before request 3, the controller may prioritize processing request 3 due to its association with the Strong Consistency Model. This delays the processing of request 2, increasing its queuing latency. In this process, while necessary for maintaining data accuracy, can introduce delays, especially in high-traffic environments. When the synchronization rate is too high, network bandwidth and system resources are heavily consumed, leading to increased response times and reduced system efficiency. Conversely, reducing synchronization frequency may lead to outdated information across nodes, affecting decision-making processes in SDN control architectures. Finding a balance between synchronization frequency and system performance remains a challenge for Atomix-based deployments.

Another limitation of Atomix is its lack of flexibility in customization. While it provides high-level abstractions for distributed data structures and messaging, these abstractions can sometimes limit the developer’s ability to fine-tune the system according to specific use cases. For example, Atomix’s default synchronization and consensus mechanisms may not always be optimal for all SDN applications. In certain scenarios, developers may want to adjust replication strategies

or modify how Atomix handles failures, but the framework does not always offer straightforward ways to implement such customizations. As a result, users may need to work around these limitations, which can add complexity to system design and maintenance.

Integrating Atomix with other SDN components also presents challenges. In many SDN architectures, Atomix is used for controller state synchronization and distributed decision-making. However, ensuring seamless integration with SDN controllers, such as ONOS, requires careful configuration. Issues such as synchronization delays, message queue bottlenecks, and compatibility problems between different Atomix versions and SDN software updates can lead to unexpected failures. Without proper tuning, the interaction between Atomix and SDN controllers may degrade overall network performance rather than improve it.

Despite these challenges, Atomix remains a valuable tool for distributed SDN architectures. However, addressing its limitations is crucial for improving the efficiency and scalability of systems that rely on it. Future improvements, such as adaptive synchronization strategies, optimized resource management, and more flexible customization options, could help mitigate these issues and enhance Atomix’s performance in large-scale distributed networks.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we investigate the impact of different data storage mechanisms on the performance of distributed SDN architectures, with a particular focus on the ONOS/Atomix framework. By analyzing various storage models, we identify key challenges in ensuring efficient data synchronization and controller performance. Our findings indicate that synchronization frequency, synchronization level, and the chosen consistency model in ONOS/Atomix significantly influence network performance, particularly in terms of flow setup time (FST) and queuing delay. The Raft-based consistency model, while ensuring strong data consistency, introduces considerable overhead, which may reduce system efficiency in large-scale networks. Furthermore, our evaluation highlights that the default random communication between the controller and data store in ONOS may not be the optimal choice for high-throughput environments. These insights provide a deeper understanding of how different data storage mechanisms affect distributed SDN performance and offer guidance for improving data consistency and retrieval efficiency in SDN deployments.

Our future work will be divided into three main phases. First, we will examine the synchronization frequency of different distributed data types in ONOS/Atomix under various topologies. This will not only reveal the consistency models used by different data types in the latest ONOS version but also allow us to compare which data types exhibit higher synchronization frequencies, laying a solid foundation for the next phase. Second, we will modify the storage mechanisms of the data types identified in the first phase as having high synchronization frequencies and evaluate their impact

by comparing FST, aiming to determine the optimal storage mechanism. The ultimate goal is to reduce the performance overhead introduced by the consistency mechanism through storage optimization, thereby enhancing the performance of the distributed SDN controller. Finally, we will conduct further experimental validation on a large-scale SDN testbed to assess the real-world applicability of our proposed enhancements, ensuring their effectiveness across diverse network environments.

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